

The Wrong Razor

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Abstract. The gold standard theory of general intelligence has a flaw. It depends on Ockham’s razor, which says simpler explanations are more likely to be true. Solomonoff translated Ockham into a mathematical ideal, which the AIXI model then made a target for AGI research. However simplicity is subjective, determined by the codebook an agent uses to encode information. This fact has been used to refute optimality claims about AIXI. Here I propose an alternative standard, one that retains AIXI’s universality without the codebook flaw. I show that on any finite hypothesis class, every strictly positive prior is an Ockham prior within a factor of two for some prefix-free code, so simplicity does not pick out an invariant of interactive intelligence at all. The quantity that does survive every recoding is the weakness of embodied constraints, which is the size of the set of further commitments still compatible with a correct policy in the agent’s embodied state. Weakest-correct is Bayes optimal under exchangeable unseen requirements. For a fixed representation M , the minimum average normalised regret is exactly the weighted forgetting cost $K_\rho(M)$, and under the canonical independent prior the optimal M -based policy generalises with probability $e^{-K_\rho(M)}$. In continuous settings, μ -weakness is reparameterisation invariant and minimax optimal over the exchangeable uncertainty class. Bennett’s razor therefore prefers the weakest correct description rather than the shortest. The interactive ideal is not a Solomonoff agent but a weakness-maximising one, namely BAGI (バギ) at fixed embodiment and UNAGI (鰻) across embodiments.

Keywords: AGI · AIXI · Solomonoff induction · Ockham’s razor · Bennett’s razor · weakness · generalisation · embodiment

Note. For readability, paper uses proof sketches. Complete proofs are at [5]: https://github.com/ViscousLemming/Technical-Appendices/blob/main/Papers/The_Wrong_Razor/The_Wrong_Razor_Appendix.pdf

1 The Wrong Invariant

Artificial General Intelligence (AGI) is often poorly defined and loosely interpreted. Mathematical definitions of AGI seek to avoid this ambiguity, and the gold standard mathematical definition is AIXI [18, 19]. It operates on the idea that simpler explanations are more likely to be correct. It uses Solomonoff induction to rank hypotheses about the world [39, 40] in terms of their Kolmogorov complexity [23, 28]. In practical model selection terms, this amounts to the Minimum Description Length principle [36, 15].

In layman’s terms, it says that if one explanation requires many more words to write down than another, then it is less likely to be true. Intelligence is compression, in other words. This view has only grown more popular [11], but it has a critical flaw. Compression depends on a codebook [3]. A language with a built-in Fibonacci primitive makes the first hundred Fibonacci numbers short in one code and long in another. The sequence does not change, only the codebook does. Embodiment amounts to a choice of codebook [3], because the body translates between the software that makes a choice the consequence of those choices.

To rectify these sorts of shortcomings, some have proposed “embedded” variants of AIXI [8, 31]. Self-Predictive Universal AI repairs the decoupled action model by making the agent predict its own actions as part of the world, and the Embedded Universal Predictive Intelligence model pushes further into embedded prediction. Commendable efforts, but they do not resolve the problem. We still end up with an agent with a non-invariant prior optimising a non-invariant objective. The same applies to the Legg-Hutter definition of universal intelligence [24] and to compression-weighted test suites [16]. Those measures inherit whatever the reference machine smuggles in.

Critics abound. Sterkenburg argues that the simplicity reading of Solomonoff induction is inessential and that the normative guidance from the ideal is “exceedingly weak” [41]. Chollet argues compression-based measures conflate skill with scope [10]. From a philosophical perspective, Sober argues that parsimony carries less epistemic weight than often assumed [38]. Even AIXI’s creator has authored a number of critiques [42, 25].

Yet there is little in the way of an alternative. My previous work sought to address this by formalising embodiment [1] and representation invariant optimality [2], but stopped short of a reinforcement learning replacement for AIXI. Here, I supply a constructive replacement.

Problem. There is something wrong with the Solomonoff family, and it is not just the much maligned incomputability [26]. It is failure of invariance. An ideal of intelligence should survive semantics-preserving recodings.

Result. On finite classes Ockham priors collapse into code choice. Without a privileged abstraction layer, intrinsic semantic length collapses into uniformity. Under exchangeable unseen-requirement growth, weakest-correct is Bayes optimal. For a fixed representation, irreducible regret is weighted forgetting, so representation loss becomes an exact odds penalty against generalisation. The same replacement survives the continuous invariance tests.

The long and short of it is that I’m going to keep AIXI’s universal ambition and replace the razor.

2 Results

Novelty relative to prior work. Weakness, the optimality of weakest-correct hypotheses, the computational dualism critique, K_ρ as weighted forgetting, and μ -weakness as a reparameterisation-invariant continuous criterion are imported from [1–3, 7, 6]. New here are the synthesis as Bennett’s razor against the interactive Solomonoff family, the finite recoding no-go corollary, the canonical-prior bridge giving $\Pr(\text{generalises}) = e^{-K_\rho(M)}$,

and BAGI/UNAGI as a named replacement ideal with an explicit outer-loop selection principle.

2.1 A finite recoding no-go theorem

AIXI and its descendants are built upon the idea that the shortest correct description is most likely to be true. However description length is not stable. The length of the shortest program for a string depends on the formalism [9]. The replacement measure is of embodied constraints or commitments, or constraint *weakness* to be exact [4]. For example, a man with his arm raised embodies different constraints upon possible futures than the same man in the same place with his arm lowered. Optimal adaptability comes from optimising for least commitment over embodied futures or completions, regardless of apparent complexity.

Proposition 1 (Every strictly positive finite prior is an Ockham prior within a factor of two). *Let H be a finite hypothesis set. For any strictly positive probability distribution Q on H , there exists a prefix-free code κ_Q such that the induced Ockham prior satisfies*

$$\frac{1}{2}Q(h) \leq P_{\kappa_Q}(h) \leq 2Q(h) \quad \text{for all } h \in H$$

Interpretation. On a finite class, every strictly positive prior can be rewritten as an Ockham prior. The burden of complexity is on the codebook, endlessly deferred to the interpreter.

Proof sketch. Choose code lengths $\ell(h) = \lceil -\log_2 Q(h) \rceil$. Kraft's inequality then holds, so there exists a prefix-free code with those lengths. After normalisation, the resulting Ockham prior differs from Q by at most a factor of two pointwise. Hence the family no-go result. \square

Corollary 1 (Finite recoding no-go). *No nontrivial shorter-is-better selector can define a representation-invariant ideal of general intelligence on finite hypothesis classes. \square*

Interpretation. If code length can realise any finite prior, then *use the Ockham prior* really means *choose a language and hide the choice*. The no free lunch theorems already showed that no learner dominates all others across all problems [46]. In comparison, my result shows that description length cannot even define a stable ranking within one finite class.

Proof sketch. Take $H = \{a, b\}$ and two prefix-free recodings, one with $\kappa(a) = 0$, $\kappa(b) = 10$ and the other with those codewords swapped. Any selector that strictly prefers the shorter code ranks a above b under the first coding and b above a under the second. \square

In the above the class does not change, but the codebook does. An even harsher limiting case is below.

Corollary 2 (Collapse under no abstraction). *If $\mathbf{v} = \mathcal{P}$, so there is no abstraction, then every statement has a singleton semantics-preserving representation of length 1. Any selector that scores policies only by that intrinsic semantic length, and treats equal scores symmetrically, therefore collapses to uniform over the candidate family [5]. \square*

Interpretation. A selector that degenerates to uniformity when abstraction is removed is measuring the code rather than the behaviour. I'm not saying that ordinary MDL secretly assigns unit length to raw objects. Rather, once no privileged abstraction is allowed, intrinsic semantic length stops discriminating policies at all.

Proof sketch. When $\mathbf{v} = \mathcal{P}$, every statement l has the singleton representation $\{T(l)\}$. All such singleton representations have the same cardinality. So any intrinsic length score is constant, and any symmetric tie rule becomes uniform. \square

This does *not* by itself refute Solomonoff induction. Kolmogorov complexity is invariant up to additive constants, and practical universal AI can restrict itself to natural reference machines [29, 20]. Leuenberger has recently defended Ockham's razor from algorithmic information theory in detail [27], and the formalism dependence can be reduced by fixing a deliberately simple reference language such as Tromp's binary lambda calculus [44]. The defence matters for passive sequence prediction, but it is far too weak for an interactive ideal. Engineering a small natural machine improves engineering, not invariance. In interactive settings those constants feed the policy ranking through the reference machine, and bad universal priors can make any policy look optimal [25]. A natural machine may be a useful engineering prior, but it is not a representation-invariant law of intelligence.

Scope. My target is the Solomonoff family as an ideal of interactive general intelligence, not classical passive Solomonoff prediction. Once the prior ranks embodied policies, reference-machine constants and vocabulary choice become decision-relevant.

2.2 Weakest-correct inside one embodiment

The replacement begins with embodiment rather than disembodied software [1]. Embodiment is really about the codebook with which one interprets the world, like the instruction set architecture of a computer. Classical statistical learning theory bounds generalisation through capacity measures such as VC dimension [45], and those bounds are representation-dependent. The question here is what happens when the representation itself is the variable. Let Φ be an environment of mutually exclusive states, let $\mathcal{P} = 2^\Phi$, and let $\mathbf{v} \subseteq \mathcal{P}$ be a finite vocabulary. The embodied language is

$$L_{\mathbf{v}} = \{l \subseteq \mathbf{v} \mid \bigcap_{p \in l} p \neq \emptyset\}.$$

For $l \in L_{\mathbf{v}}$, define its extension by

$$\text{Ext}(l) = \{y \in L_{\mathbf{v}} \mid l \subseteq y\}, \quad \text{Ext}(X) = \bigcup_{x \in X} \text{Ext}(x) \text{ for } X \subseteq L_{\mathbf{v}}.$$

A task is a pair $\alpha = \langle I_{\alpha}, O_{\alpha} \rangle$ with $I_{\alpha} \subseteq L_{\mathbf{v}}$ and $O_{\alpha} \subseteq \text{Ext}(I_{\alpha})$. A policy $\pi \in L_{\mathbf{v}}$ is correct exactly when

$$\text{Ext}(I_{\alpha}) \cap \text{Ext}(\pi) = O_{\alpha}.$$

Write Π_{α} for the set of correct policies. Its weakness is

$$w(\pi) = |\text{Ext}(\pi)|.$$

Interpretation. Weakness counts how many further commitments remain available while the policy stays correct. It is how *weakly constrained* the system is. It is least

commitment stated in the learner’s own embodied language. A commitment here is just a constraint the policy ties itself to, so weakness is the number of constraint-bundles still compatible with the policy.

Rote memorisation and weakness. For a bit of intuitive understanding of what weakness is, consider how it compares to rote memorisation. A policy is a statement $\pi \in L_{\mathbf{v}}$, a bundle of commitments, and its extension $\text{Ext}(\pi)$ is the set of bundles that still contain it. Permitting every continuation means committing to almost nothing, which does make the extension large, but it breaks correctness, because such a policy also extends to wrong outputs on the seen inputs and so fails $\text{Ext}(I_{\alpha}) \cap \text{Ext}(\pi) = O_{\alpha}$. Rote memorising observed data is the opposite. It pins many specific propositions into π , and adding commitments can only shrink the extension, never grow it, since $\pi \subseteq \pi'$ forces $\text{Ext}(\pi') \subseteq \text{Ext}(\pi)$. So the memoriser is highly committed and not weak. The weakest correct policy commits to exactly enough to stay correct on the seen data and no more.

Suppose the learner has seen only a child task α . Let $U := L_{\mathbf{v}} \setminus \text{Ext}(I_{\alpha})$ be the unseen region. For a correct child policy π , write $B_{\pi} := \text{Ext}(\pi) \cap U$ for its buffer. The exchangeable unseen-requirement model keeps correctness on the seen slice fixed and draws a random set $S \subseteq U$ of additional unseen requirements. Conditional on $|S|$, every subset of U of that size is equally likely.

Theorem 1 (Weakest-correct is Bayes optimal). *Fix a finite vocabulary \mathbf{v} and a child task α . Under the exchangeable unseen-requirement model, let*

$$\pi^* \in \arg \max_{\pi \in \Pi_{\alpha}} w(\pi).$$

Then

$$P(S \subseteq B_{\pi^*} \mid \alpha) = \max_{\pi \in \Pi_{\alpha}} P(S \subseteq B_{\pi} \mid \alpha).$$

More generally, among all selectors supported on Π_{α} , the weakest-correct rule maximises expected survival probability [3, 5].

Interpretation. If you do not know which unseen constraints the future will impose, keep the largest number of possible correct (desirable) futures open. In this setting shortest-correct is not Bayes optimal, but weakest-correct is.

Proof sketch. A correct policy survives exactly when the unseen additions S land inside its buffer B_{π} . For correct policies the seen part is fixed, so¹ $\text{Ext}(\pi) = O_{\alpha} \sqcup B_{\pi}$ and $w(\pi) = |O_{\alpha}| + |B_{\pi}|$. Conditional on $|S| = k$, every k -subset of U is equally likely, so

$$P(S \subseteq B_{\pi} \mid \alpha, |S| = k) = \binom{|B_{\pi}|}{k} / \binom{|U|}{k},$$

which is monotone in $|B_{\pi}|$ and therefore in $w(\pi)$. \square

Parent-task reading. If one packages the unseen requirement set S into a parent-task construction that leaves the seen slice fixed, then the same event is the usual statement that the child policy is also correct for the parent. The proof itself only needs compatibility with S .

¹ Where \sqcup means disjoint union. Means the two sets being combined share no elements.

Toy example. Suppose two correct policies agree on the seen region, but π_1 leaves three unseen completions in U open while π_2 leaves one. If exactly one unseen requirement arrives uniformly from U , then π_1 survives with probability $3/|U|$ and π_2 with probability $1/|U|$.

2.3 Regret is the outer loop over representations

A universal ideal needs more than a rule for choosing a policy inside one embodiment. It also needs a rule for evaluating representations. Hence my recent reinforcement-learning results, which provide an exact defect variable for that outer loop [7].

Fix a representation M and quotient history-test pairs by the cells $(M(h), T)$. Let μ_i be evaluation weights, let $\delta_i(\pi)$ be normalised regret, let ρ_i be the corresponding margin weights, and let $y_i \in \{0, 1\}$ denote the optimal bet on support point i . For a cell C , write A_C for the weighted case that C should bet 1 and B_C for the weighted case that it should bet 0. Then the best any M -based policy can do is given exactly by weighted forgetting.

Theorem 2 (Exact reduction, regret is weighted forgetting). *For every fixed representation M ,*

$$\inf_{\pi \text{ is } M\text{-based}} \sum_i \mu_i \delta_i(\pi) = K_\rho(M) = \sum_{C \in \mathcal{C}_M} \min\{A_C, B_C\},$$

where

$$A_C := \sum_{i \in C, y_i=1} \mu_i \rho_i, \quad B_C := \sum_{i \in C, y_i=0} \mu_i \rho_i.$$

The same number is the weighted weakness deficit of a lifted diagnostic task built from the evaluation support, so the RL regret floor and the Stack-Theoretic forgetting cost are literally the same object [7, 5].

Interpretation. Once you quotient by representation-test cell, regret is exactly the cheapest weighted deletion needed to make the correct bet single-valued. The optimal M -based policy does not merely match the cost of forgetting. Cell by cell, it performs forgetting by discarding the cheaper label class.

Proof sketch. On a fixed cell C , expected regret is the affine function $A_C(1 - q_C) + B_C q_C$. The minimum over $q_C \in [0, 1]$ is therefore attained at an endpoint and equals $\min\{A_C, B_C\}$. Making the correct label single-valued on that same cell requires deleting one whole label class. The cheapest such deletion again costs $\min\{A_C, B_C\}$. Summing over cells gives the identity. \square

Corollary 3 (Any policy splits into structural regret and avoidable regret). *Let $q_C \in [0, 1]$ be an actual policy's report probability of betting on outcome 1 on cell C , and for each cell choose any*

$$q_C^* \in \arg \min_{q \in [0, 1]} (A_C(1 - q) + B_C q).$$

Then every M -based policy satisfies

$$\sum_i \mu_i \delta_i(\pi) = K_\rho(M) + \sum_{C \in \mathcal{C}_M} |A_C - B_C| |q_C - q_C^*|.$$

In particular,

$$K_\rho(M) \leq \sum_i \mu_i \delta_i(\pi),$$

with equality exactly when the policy is cellwise optimal on every non-tied cell [7, 5]. \square

Interpretation. This separates structural aliasing cost from within-cell misreporting. One part of the error comes from the representation. The rest comes from what you did with it.

Proof sketch. On each cell, subtract the cellwise minimum from the affine regret expression. What remains is an absolute-value term with coefficient $|A_C - B_C|$. Summing those cellwise residues gives the decomposition. \square

Toy example. Take three equally weighted support points under one test T with optimal labels $(1, 0, 0)$ and unit margins $\rho_i = 1$. If M_1 puts all three points in one cell, then $A_C = 1/3$, $B_C = 2/3$, and $K_\rho(M_1) = 1/3$. If M_2 separates x_1 from $\{x_2, x_3\}$, every cell is pure and $K_\rho(M_2) = 0$. The first representation carries an irreducible regret floor of $1/3$. The second does not.

The bridge then cashes out as a generalisation statement. Under the canonical independent relevance prior, each support point i is independently relevant with probability $r_i := 1 - e^{-\mu_i \rho_i}$. It is canonical in the narrow sense that independence across support points plus exact recovery of the additive forgetting cost forces the survival factor $e^{-\mu_i \rho_i}$. Hence $\Pr(D \text{ survives}) = \prod_{i \in D} (1 - r_i) = e^{-\sum_{i \in D} \mu_i \rho_i}$.

Corollary 4 (Generalisation probability from regret). *Under the canonical independent prior,*

$$\Pr(\text{optimal } M\text{-based policy generalises}) = e^{-K_\rho(M)}.$$

[7, 5].

Interpretation. Representation quality becomes survival probability. In the toy example, M_1 therefore generalises with probability $e^{-1/3}$, while M_2 generalises with probability 1.

Proof sketch. The exact bridge writes $K_\rho(M)$ as the total weight of the discarded diagnostic outputs. Under the canonical independent prior, generalisation means none of those discarded outputs become relevant. Independence makes the survival probability factorise, and the special choice $r_i = 1 - e^{-\mu_i \rho_i}$ turns that product into $e^{-K_\rho(M)}$.

Zero irreducible regret requires the representation-test partition to refine the coarsest pure diagnostic partition \mathcal{P}_+^* , so informative-minimal zero-regret representations coincide up to relabelling on the informative support [7]. \square

2.4 The invariance sanity check

The flat minima debate supplies a sanity check rather than the main positive case. Hochreiter and Schmidhuber proposed that flat minima generalise better than sharp

ones [17]. That idea became an industry. Keskar et al. linked large-batch training to sharp minima and poor generalisation [22]. Foret et al. built Sharpness-Aware Minimisation on the same intuition [14]. But Dinh et al. showed that function-preserving reparameterisations can make any minimum arbitrarily sharp without changing predictions [12]. Petzka et al. proposed relative flatness as a partial repair [34]. Jiang et al. surveyed dozens of generalisation measures and found that none reliably predicted held-out performance across architectures [21]. The pattern is that a candidate measure can only be serious if it survives semantics-preserving recodings. That is not enough to prove the survivor *right*, but it is enough to prove its encoding-sensitive rivals wrong.

For the continuous theory, fix a measurable embodied language $(\mathbf{v}, \mathcal{A}_L, \mu)$, a task α , the unseen region $U := L_{\mathbf{v}} \setminus \text{Ext}(I_{\alpha})$, and the buffer $B_{\pi} := \text{Ext}(\pi) \cap U$ of a correct policy π . Assume $0 < \mu(U) < \infty$ and $\mu(O_{\alpha}) < \infty$. Let \mathcal{E} be the class of μ -exchangeable, null-insensitive extension models on U , where null-insensitive means $\Pr(S \subseteq B) = \Pr(S \subseteq B')$ whenever $\mu(B \Delta B') = 0$.

Theorem 3 (Continuous weakest-correct remains optimal). *Under the continuous μ -exchangeable, null-insensitive model, correct policies are ordered by buffer measure $\mu(B_{\pi})$. A μ -weakest correct policy is therefore pointwise optimal for every nondegenerate model in \mathcal{E} and minimax over the whole class [5, 6].*

Interpretation. The continuous theory says the same thing as the finite one. Only the measure changes. If you know nothing about which unseen measurable region will matter next beyond its size, the least committal correct policy still wins.

Proof sketch. Exchangeability plus null-insensitivity makes the generalisation score depend only on $\mu(B_{\pi})$. Nondegeneracy makes that dependence strict. So a policy with maximal buffer measure dominates pointwise over \mathcal{E} . Pointwise dominance immediately gives the minimax claim.

Let $F(\theta)$ be the function computed by parameters θ , and define $\Pi_F(\theta) = \{p \in \mathbf{v} \mid F(\theta) \text{ satisfies } p\}$. If ϕ is function-preserving, then $F(\phi(\theta)) = F(\theta)$ by definition. \square

Theorem 4 (Weakness is reparameterisation invariant). *If ϕ is function-preserving, then $\Pi_F(\phi(\theta)) = \Pi_F(\theta)$ and hence $w_{\mu}(\Pi_F(\phi(\theta))) = w_{\mu}(\Pi_F(\theta))$.*

Interpretation. If two parameter settings compute the same function, then they imply the same policy and the same weakness. Schmidhuber proposed selecting neural networks by Kolmogorov complexity as a route to generalisation [37]. But Kolmogorov complexity inherits the reference machine, so the same instability reappears. In the corresponding flat-minima experiments, function-preserving reparameterisations inflated Hessian trace by roughly two orders of magnitude without changing accuracy [6]. The quantity that matters therefore lives in function space, not weight space.

Proof sketch. A function-preserving reparameterisation leaves the realised input-output map unchanged. The policy map depends only on which programs that realised function satisfies. So the policy itself is unchanged, and the extension measure is unchanged with it.

Write $P_U := \mu|_U / \mu(U)$ and $Q_{\pi} := \mu|_{B_{\pi}} / \mu(B_{\pi})$. \square

Corollary 5 (PAC-Bayes ordering agrees with μ -weakness). *For any correct policy π with $\mu(B_\pi) > 0$, $\text{KL}(Q_\pi \| P_U) = \log \frac{\mu(U)}{\mu(B_\pi)}$. Hence standard zero-empirical-risk PAC-Bayes bounds rank correct policies exactly by buffer measure and therefore by μ -weakness [6, 5]. \square*

Interpretation. PAC-Bayes theory originated with McAllester’s model-averaging bounds [30]. Dziugaite and Roy showed those bounds can be made nonvacuous even for overparameterised deep networks [13]. Neyshabur et al. explored what drives generalisation in deep learning and found that norm-based and sharpness-based measures each fail under some reparameterisation [33]. The corollary above shows this is because the KL term collapses to one log-ratio in the zero-empirical-risk case, and that ratio is exactly the weakness gap.

Proof sketch. The Radon-Nikodym derivative of Q_π with respect to P_U is constant on B_π and equal to $\mu(U)/\mu(B_\pi)$. The KL integral therefore collapses to the log of that constant. Any zero-empirical-risk PAC-Bayes bound that is monotone in the KL term must then rank policies by decreasing $\mu(B_\pi)$.

Using a global prior on all of L_v instead of the restricted prior on U only adds a policy-independent constant to the KL term [5]. The ordering is unchanged. \square

3 The replacement ideal

Ockham’s razor says prefer the shortest correct description. The replacement is Bennett’s razor, which is to prefer the weakest correct description [3]. Weakness is the property that survives every invariance test that description length fails.

At fixed embodiment, BAGI chooses a weakest correct policy for the current embodied task [3, 5]. Across a vocabulary class V , UNAGI searches over admissible embodiments $\mathbf{v} \in V$, each with induced representation $M_{\mathbf{v}}$.

Selection principle. First maximise task-level utility over $\mathbf{v} \in V$. Among the utility-maximising embodiments, choose one with minimal $K_\rho(M_{\mathbf{v}})$. Inside that winning embodiment, choose a weakest correct policy for the task induced there.

Interpretation. The old ideal searched over codes while holding embodiment fixed. The new one searches over embodiments, prices representation loss exactly, then chooses the correct policy that keeps the largest future open. Richens et al. recently argued that general agents require world models [35]. The UNAGI construction agrees in spirit but replaces the model-selection criterion. The world model matters only insofar as its vocabulary determines K_ρ .

3.1 What one step looks like

The Solomonoff family is concrete enough to admit AIXI as its named ideal and computable approximations as engineering targets. A credible replacement needs to offer the same. I sketch one step of each agent in plain language. These sketches are formal descriptions, rather than actual implementations.

BAGI at fixed embodiment. A BAGI step at fixed vocabulary \mathbf{v} and child task $\alpha = \langle I_\alpha, O_\alpha \rangle$ proceeds in four operations.

1. Enumerate the set of correct policies $\Pi_\alpha = \{\pi \in L_{\mathbf{v}} \mid \text{Ext}(I_\alpha) \cap \text{Ext}(\pi) = O_\alpha\}$ from the seen data.
2. For each candidate π , compute or estimate its weakness $w(\pi) = |\text{Ext}(\pi)|$ in the embodied language.
3. Return any $\pi^* \in \arg \max_{\pi \in \Pi_\alpha} w(\pi)$.
4. Act on the next input by using π^* .

This is the embodied analogue of the Solomonoff posterior step. It replaces shortest-correct with weakest-correct and computes the latter directly inside the agent’s own vocabulary rather than inside a fixed external reference machine. For an AIXI reader the upgrade path is to swap the universal prior over programs for an extension count over the embodied language and to swap shortest-correct selection for weakest-correct selection. Everything else, including the planning loop over actions, can be left in place.

UNAGI across embodiments. A UNAGI step over an admissible vocabulary class V proceeds in five operations.

1. For each $\mathbf{v} \in V$, induce the task and the representation $M_{\mathbf{v}}$ and run the BAGI inner loop on it.
2. Score each embodiment by realised task-level utility under the chosen weakest-correct policy.
3. Restrict to the utility-maximising embodiments $V^* \subseteq V$.
4. Among those, compute $K_\rho(M_{\mathbf{v}})$ and keep any $\mathbf{v}^* \in V^*$ with minimal K_ρ .
5. Return \mathbf{v}^* together with its weakest correct policy.

This is the outer loop the Solomonoff family does not have. AIXI holds embodiment fixed at the chosen universal machine and searches over programs. UNAGI searches over embodiments and pays the exact K_ρ price for any cell-collisions the embodiment forces on the agent. The two scores are not interchangeable. Task utility is what the agent already wanted. K_ρ is the exact forgetting cost the embodiment imposes on the next task. Tied utility is the regime where the embodiment with cleaner cells wins, because it carries less irreducible regret into future tasks.

Computability comments. BAGI and UNAGI are ideals in the same sense as Solomonoff induction. Exact enumeration of Π_α and exact computation of $w(\pi)$ may be intractable in many cases, but they are at least computable. Solomonoff induction is not. Tractable approximations of the inner enumeration and approximations of w by sampled extension counts. Bennett’s razor is therefore a statement against approximating the wrong quantity, rather than any sort of opposition to approximation itself.

4 Discussion

This paper targets the interactive Solomonoff family, where policy ranking must survive changes of codebook and embodiment. On that target AIXI wielded the wrong razor. On finite classes description length does not determine a unique inductive law. In interactive settings the reference-machine constant is decision-relevant. In continuous settings encoding-sensitive surrogates fail the invariance test again. The double descent

phenomenon, where bigger models and more data can temporarily hurt performance, further undermines any monotone complexity-based ranking [32].

Tenenbaum et al. argued that growing a mind requires structured hierarchical representations rather than flat compression [43]. The weakness framework addresses the same dissatisfaction but from a different direction. What matters is not how short the representation is but how many correct (desirable) futures it keeps open.

Bennett’s razor replaces Ockham’s. Inside one embodiment choose the weakest correct policy. Across embodiments maximise task-level utility, break ties by smaller $K_\rho(M)$, then choose the weakest correct policy inside the winner. Simplicity can still correlate with persistence, but only when embodiments or selection pressures pack weak policies into simple forms [2, 3]. Keep the universal ambition, but drop the hidden codebook in interactive settings. An optimal agent should not interact with the Solomonoff family.

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